

Versatile Video Coding Performance Evaluation for Tiled 360° Videos

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Abstract—Recently, virtual reality (VR) and 360° videos have been increasingly adopted in a wide range of applications. However, the huge sizes of 360° videos necessitate the use of powerful compression tools to allow for efficient storage and streaming of these videos. In this article, we compare the performance of four different video codecs, including AV1 and versatile video coding (VVC), when applied to a dataset of 360° videos. We conduct our evaluation according to peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR)-based 360° video quality assessment (VQA) metrics. As omnidirectional videos are usually streamed as independent tiles, we also investigate the tiling effect on VVC compression performance by comparing full-frame-based compression to tiled segment compression using grids of 8x8 and 16x16 tiles.

Keywords—360° videos, video compression, video streaming, virtual reality (VR).

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, 360° videos and virtual reality (VR) applications have been utilized in a variety of domains. Users wearing head-mounted displays (HMDs) can freely move their heads to view the video content in the preferred directions. As omnidirectional videos were developed to place the users in an immersive environment, they tend to have huge sizes and bitrates. Ensuring a high quality of experience (QoE) is subject to strict requirements as ultra-high-definition resolutions (4K or higher) need to be provided to the users. This in turn creates a challenge for storing and streaming these types of videos [1]. Therefore, powerful compression schemes need to be applied to reduce the size of 360° videos to more reasonable levels. Although popular video codecs were primarily designed to target 2D videos, they can also be utilized for encoding 360° videos after being projected into equivalent 2D shapes. Among these codecs is AV1 [2], which was developed by the Alliance for Open Media (AOM) to succeed the VP9 encoder. Whereas Versatile Video Coding (VVC) [3] was released in 2020 by the Joint Video Exploration Team (JVET) to improve over its successors, the Advanced Video Coding (AVC) and the High-Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) [4] standards.

In the context of 360° video streaming, the ERP-projected video is typically divided into a grid of independent rectangular tiles as illustrated in Figure 1. Tiles are then encoded and transmitted independently, which introduces a new degree of streaming flexibility. As the user watches only a part of the overall spherical scene at a time, only tiles that correspond to his/her field of view (FoV) need to be delivered [5], [6]. Increasing the number of tiles within the grid increases streaming flexibility and allows for bandwidth reduction. However, dividing the video into small tiles can result in lower compression efficiency as compression opportunities across different tiles would be missed.

Figure 1: ERP transformation and tiling of a 360° video.

Video compression naturally introduces several artifacts that affect the quality of the videos, where the severity of the quality drop depends on the compression level. Many video quality assessment (VQA) methods have been proposed to evaluate encoded video quality. The peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) metric provides a simple full-reference VQA metric that compares individual pixel values of the original uncompressed video frames to those of the compressed video. However, with 360° videos, the relationship between the spherical watching space and the 2D encoding space is nonlinear. This makes the direct calculation of PSNR less reliable as an indication of the perceived quality. Consequently, different variations of PSNR-based 360° VQA metrics have been developed to account for the mapping nonuniformity and to better estimate the spherical video quality. The spherical PSNR (S-PSNR) [7] compares the pixel values of the reference and original frames depending on their corresponding uniformly-sampled spheres, which allows for

the evaluation of videos with different panoramic projections. In weighted-to-spherically-uniform PSNR (WS-PSNR), pixel value differences are calculated similarly to PSNR and weighted depending on their positions within the scene [8]. The Crasters parabolic projection (CPP-PSNR) [9] transforms the video frames into the Crasters parabolic projection format before calculating the PSNR values. Hence, it can be used even if the reference and impaired frames have different projection formats and resolutions.

In this article, we first compare the performance of four video codecs according to PSNR-based 360° VQA metrics. Specifically, we use open-source implementations of VP9, AV1, HEVC, and VVC and evaluate their compression efficiency when applied to a dataset of 360° videos. After that, we proceed to study VVC compression performance when used for encoding tiled 360° video segments compared to the case of full-frame segmented videos. The experiment procedure and evaluation results of the four video codecs performance assessment are provided in section II. Section III discusses the tiling and segmentation details and presents the results of VVC tile-based compression. Finally, we summarize and conclude our work in section IV.

II. 360° VIDEO ENCODING

In this section, we provide details with respect to our experimental setup and present the results for 360° video compression. First, we describe the 360° video dataset chosen in our work. Then we give more details on the encoders' implementations and the encoding parameters used for compression. We also explain the adopted VQA metrics and provide a discussion on the obtained results.

A. Dataset

We carried out our evaluation based on the ODV-VQA dataset [10]. We selected the twelve 360° videos which are provided in raw format and used them as reference sequences. The videos belong to different categories. Each of these videos is ten seconds long and has a framerate of 30fps. Ten of these videos have a resolution of 4096x2048 and the other two have

a resolution of 3840x1920. Table 1 summarizes the selected reference videos. The ODV-VQA dataset also provides head movement (HM) and eye gaze movement (EM) traces, collected from users watching the videos using HMDs.

Table 1: Dataset summary.

Video Title	Resolution & Frame Rate	Dur. (sec)	Size (GB)
PressConference	4096x2048 @ 30fps	10	3.51
Shooting	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
Pagoda	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
Salon	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
ConcertLive	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
DrivingInCity	3840x1920 @ 30fps		3.08
FootballMatch	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
GreatWall	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
BoatInPark	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
BuddhaCave	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51
DrivingInCountry	3840x1920 @ 30fps		3.08
XiaoGuang	4096x2048 @ 30fps		3.51

B. Methodology

We used four encoding methods to compress the twelve selected 360° videos which are projected into the ERP format with yuv420p pixel representation. The four codecs used in this section are VP9, AV1, HEVC, and VVC. We used libvpx-vp9 build available in ffmpeg [11] for VP9 compression. We also used SVT-AV1 [12], x265 [13], and Fraunhofer's VVenC [14] as implementations for AV1, HEVC, and VVC, respectively. We chose to work with VVenC as it provides an optimized framework with a significant running time reduction over the VTM reference implementation [15]. We set the compression parameters for all codecs to allow for a fair comparison and selected the quantization parameter (QP) values {22, 27, 32, 37} for x265 and VVenC, and the QP values {27, 35, 46, 55} for the VP9 and AV1 video codecs.

(a): Y-values.

(b): Global values.

Figure 2: Rate-distortion curves. Encoding comparison between VP9, x265, AV1, and VVC based on Y-values and global values of PSNR, S-PSNR, WS-PSNR, and CPP-PSNR.

TABLE II: BR-Rates based on global VQA metrics values.

Encoding	AV1	X265	VP9
VVC	7.858%	41.98%	43.68%
AV1	-	31.21%	33.358%
X265	-	-	2.90%

(a) PSNR

Encoding	AV1	X265	VP9
VVC	5.29%	39.74%	41.81%
AV1	-	29.90%	32.68%
X265	-	-	3.29%

(b) S-PSNR

Encoding	AV1	X265	VP9
VVC	4.03%	40.44%	42.06%
AV1	-	31.20%	33.40%
X265	-	-	2.72%

(c) WS-PSNR

Encoding	AV1	X265	VP9
VVC	5.07%	39.87	42.13
AV1	-	30.07	33.06
X265	-	-	3.63

(d) CPP-PSNR

C. Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the different encoding methods when applied to 360° videos, we utilized Samsung’s 360tools [16] to compute the PSNR, S-PSNR, WS-PSNR, and CPP-PSNR values. For each metric, we calculated the luma values ($PSNR_Y$) and the global PSNR values ($PSNR_{611}$) which also includes the chroma values ($PSNR_U$ and $PSNR_V$) to better depict the perceived quality of the videos. The global PSNR values, similarly for all PSNR variations, are hence calculated as follows:

$$PSNR_{611} = (6 * PSNR_Y + PSNR_U + PSNR_V) / 8$$

Moreover, to compute the bitrate reduction at equivalent performance, we calculated the BD-Rate Bjontegaard metric [17] values for all the global metrics values. The BD-rate is an insightful metric used to numerically compare two different encoding standards. The calculation of BD-rates involves fitting the bitrate-PSNR curves using third-order polynomials. The average difference in bitrate values is hence obtained by computing the area between the two resulting curves.

After encoding the selected 360° videos and evaluating the discussed quality metrics, we obtained the rate-distortion curves and the BD-rate tables to compare the four different codecs used in our experiment. The rate-distortion curves based on the Y-values and on global values for PSNR, S-PSNR, WS-PSNR, and CPP-PSNR are all illustrated in Figure 2. Whereas the BD-Rate values are depicted in Table II. Based on the acquired results, VVC outperforms the three other video codecs in all the calculated quality metrics. Specifically, VVC results in bitrate reduction over AV1 with 7.858%, 5.29%, 4.03%, and 5.07% when assessed using PSNR, S-PSNR, WS-PSNR, and CPP-PSNR, respectively. VVC also achieves equivalent quality metric values to both x265 and VP9 with a bitrate reduction of ~40%. AV1 leads to a marginal compression efficiency enhancement over x265 and VP9, as it results in a +30% bitrate reduction according to all the presented metrics.

D. VQ Analyzer – VVC Encoding Visualization

VQ analyzer [18] visualizes each step of the encoding process and associated tools used on a per-frame basis. Figure 3 depicts an example of an extracted encoded image with the VVC encoder. Additional informational overlays such as the QP Map and the Coding Tree Unit (CTU) structure can be added and displayed on the video image, to visualize and

provide a perceptual understanding of the underlying video coding algorithms. The QP Map shows the per-block QP. Finer CTU levels, i.e., smaller blocks, are typically formed around areas of interest or non-homogeneous high-motion image regions. When the movement in one CU is detected, the CU is split into smaller CUs, and the depth in the quadtree of the selected CU increases. An example in the present frame is that of the football player area and its vicinity. It should be noted that the depicted modes vary and change with respect to the frame sequence, picture subtype (I, P, and B frames), and mode used (i.e., intra or inter mode).

III. TILED 360° VIDEO COMPRESSION

In 360° video streaming, equirectangular projected videos are typically segmented into short-time segments and divided into independent rectangular tiles before the encoding and transmission processes. However, dividing the video into small-sized tiles can degrade the compression efficiency as it loses some of the compression opportunities. For instance, an object moving across two different tiles will not benefit from the inter-prediction-based encoding when the two tiles are compressed independently. Therefore, in this section, we investigate the effect of tiling on the overall compression efficiency. We focus our evaluation on the VVC encoder and assess the performance of tiled 8x8 and 16x16 grids compared to the full-frame encoding approach.

A. Temporal Segmentation

Video streaming protocols, such as MPEG-DASH [19], break the video content into segments (2-10 seconds) to ensure efficient use of bandwidth and to perform adaptive streaming. In the case of 360° videos, however, users continuously change their viewing direction which translates to changes in their watched content over time. Therefore, opting for long temporal segmentation can obstruct the utilization of viewport-dependent transmission. Oftentimes, viewport prediction methods [20]-[22] are utilized to provide an estimation of future watching directions and to allow for proactive transmission. Although modern viewport prediction methods can forecast viewing directions with high accuracy for hundreds of milliseconds in advance, their performance degrades as the prediction window is increased.

Therefore, before choosing the segmentation length of the videos, we decided to analyze the change in users’ viewing directions when watching the videos used in our experiment.

Figure 3: Snapshot from VQ Analyzer, showing the Shooting 360° video in Info Overlays Mode.

We utilized the head movement traces, represented by yaw and pitch angles, which are provided by [10]. Specifically, we studied the changes in viewing angles within time intervals of 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 5.0 seconds. For each case of these intervals, we calculated the maximum occurring difference in pitch and yaw angles according to the available HM data. It should be noted that as the watching space spreads over the 360°x180° spherical scene, the maximum possible change in yaw and pitch angles are 180° and 90°, respectively. In Figure 4, we show the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the calculated maximum angle changes for each case. We observe that changes in the yaw angle are more dominant than changes in the pitch angle as horizontal explorations are more common when watching omnidirectional videos. As expected, increasing the observing window results in higher angle changes. When the observing time interval is set to 1s, around 90% of the yaw maximum change is under 50°, whereas the yaw changes increase rapidly when it is set to 2 and 5 seconds.

As a trade-off based on these results, we decided to cut the videos into 1s length segments to be encoded independently. The choice of a one-second time segmentation is practical for 360° video streaming as it allows for efficient inter-frame encoding and robust transmission while also maintaining a reasonable watching length that respects changes in users' viewports. Moreover, limiting the segments' lengths to 1s allows for the utilization of accurate viewport predictions to transmit all the tiles that are expected to be viewed within this period. To anticipate prediction errors and uncertainties that can occur with this setting, a reasonable additional margin (e.g., viewport's neighboring tiles) can be transmitted in addition to the current and forecasted tiles. Some 360° video streaming strategies approach the prediction errors by transmitting content outside the expected FoVs but at lower qualities. This, therefore, avoids cases where users might end up viewing black or empty regions.

To temporally divide the videos into time segments of one-second lengths, we used ffmpeg to break each video into 10 independent segments. We used the resulting segments as references for our next evaluation steps. First, we encoded the full-frame segments using the VVC codec and obtained the corresponding 360° VQA metrics described in section II. The

resulting 360° VQA metrics values are then compared to those of tiled segments which are described in the next subsection.

Figure 4: Time segmentation and HM analysis. CDF for the maximum HM change in yaw and pitch angles within time intervals of 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 5.0 seconds.

B. Video Tiling

Partitioning 360° video into independent tiles is a common approach for immersive video delivery. A huge bandwidth reduction can be achieved by transmitting only the tiles associated with the user's FoV. Moreover, humans tend to

focus their attention on specific engaging parts of the spherical videos [23], usually located near the equator, which results in a high correlation among their FoVs. Such observations are essential for designing tiled 360° video transmission algorithms in settings where multiple users, sharing common network resources, consume the same video content [24], [25].

Figure 5: HM analysis. Heatmaps showing the center tiles for the XiaoGuang and the Shooting videos.

Before tiling the video segments, we conducted an analysis to illustrate user behavior while watching the videos used in our experiment. Based on the HM traces provided by [10], we show two viewing heatmaps for two of the videos, namely, the XiaoGuang and the Shooting 360° videos, in Figure 5, snapshots taken from the two videos are provided along with the viewing heatmaps obtained based on 20 users' HM data over the length of the videos (600 timestamps in 10 seconds). The visualization in this Figure is based on a grid of 8x8. However, it should be noted that the two heatmaps were obtained based on the center viewing tiles, where the overall

viewed tiles can be acquired similarly depending on the FoV angle specifications of the used HMDs.

In our experiment, we used ffmpeg to cut the video segments into grids of independent rectangular tiles of equal sizes, e.g., a 4096x2048 video segment divided into 8x8 tiles with 512x256 pixel resolution each. We performed the tiling using 8x8 and 16x16 grids. The tile-based compression is then performed and assessed to be compared to the compressed full-frame segments.

C. Evaluation of Tiled 360° Video Compression

After dividing the video segments into tile grids, we compressed each of the resulting tiles separately with VVenC and used ffmpeg to stitch them back to reconstruct the whole video segments. We computed the quality metrics, as discussed in section II, of all video segments and compared the tiled cases to the full-frame compression approach.

As depicted in Figure 6, the rate-distortion curves show that tiled segments lead to lower overall compression efficiency compared to full-frame-based encoding. Moreover, increasing the tiling level from 8x8 to 16x16 resulted in a further performance reduction. Even though the same QP parameters {22, 27, 32, 37} were used for all cases, the tiled video segments resulted in higher overall bitrate values.

Tiling allows for the flexible transmission of 360° videos. Depending on the users' FoVs, only a subset of the overall tiles needs to be delivered. Consequently, substantial bandwidth reductions can be achieved by tile-based viewport-dependent streaming. Although tiling results in lower compression efficiency, the advantages gained by tile-based streaming can highly outweigh this drop in encoding performance. Nonetheless, the choice of tiling levels should take the encoding performance into consideration to attain the utmost overall gains.

(a): Y-values.

(b): Global values.

Figure 6: Rate-distortion curves. Encoding comparison between full-frame, 8x8 grid, and 16x16 grid compression based on Y-values and global values of PSNR, S-PSNR, WS-PSNR, and CPP-PSNR.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we studied video compression of 360° videos. We evaluated the performance of VP9, AV1, HEVC, and VVC implementations when applied to a set of omnidirectional videos that were selected from the ODV-VQA dataset. Based on 360° VQA metrics, we reported that VVC surpasses all the other codecs, while AV1 also substantially outperforms VP9 and HVEC. We continued our study by evaluating the impact of tiling on 360° video compression using the VVC encoder. We compared the compression efficiency of tiled 360° videos to full-frame-based encoding. Our findings showed how tiling results in higher overall bitrates, which increase with smaller tile sizes. Although the bitrate increase can be justified by the benefits of tile-based 360° video streaming, a trade-off between compression efficiency and streaming flexibility should be considered to achieve optimized performance.

As part of our future work, we plan to investigate the utilization of viewport information in the compression process and extend our evaluation of 360° VQA to include viewport-dependent metrics. Hereafter, we will utilize our findings to work on the potential optimization of 360° video delivery schemes.

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